

FACTORS AFFECTING THE INTEREST IN LEARNING AMONG INTERMEDIATE PUPILS OF PANGLIMAESTINO DISTRICT, MINISTRY OF BASIC, HIGHER AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION – SULU

Sarkim S. Abdul

Marsada Primary School, Marsada Panglima Estino, Sulu

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ABSTRACT

The study is a descriptive research which deals with the factors affecting the interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Division of Sulu. The study delves into the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants, including age, gender, grade level, parental educational attainment, and average monthly income. Additionally, it examines the impact of teacher-related, student-related, and home-related factors on intermediate students' learning interest in Panglima Estino District, MBHTE - Division of Sulu. It also deals with the significant difference in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Division of Sulu when data are grouped according to socio – demographic profile in terms of age, gender, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income, and the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Division of Sulu in the context of teacher – related factor, pupils – related factor, and home – related factor. The study employed a purposive sampling approach to pick its respondents. It was discovered that the intermediate students are the appropriate age for their current grade level, that the number of students from each gender was equal, and that the parents are low-income and lack formal education. The factors always affect the interest in learning in terms of teacher – related factor and pupils – related factor and often affect in terms of home – related factor. There is no significant difference in terms of demographic profile. There is a moderate correlation among the three factors.

Keywords: *Factors affecting the interest, intermediate pupils, MBHTE-SULU, Panglima Estino District, Descriptive research.*

INTRODUCTION

Everyday obstacles and transformations serve as a kind of education. In the current globalized society, we need to be prepared for everything, particularly in the area of education, as this is one of the cornerstones for developing the human capital required to meet a variety of difficulties in the future. Safitri Desi, et al. (2023).

In teaching and learning everyone expects a better output and excellent performance on the part of teachers and pupils. However, a student's academic success is influenced by a variety of elements, whether they are personal, educational, or connected to the teacher. Change in human development is characterized by a number of factors, including continuity, accumulation, direction, differentiation, organization, and holism. Development may also fluctuate over time. made the point that a person's experience is influenced by the family, societal, and cultural context of their upbringing. The failure of their children can be attributed to parents who are slow to respond to schoolwork, show no concern for their children's schoolwork, or skip lessons.

Maslow's 1943 work, which Jerald Moneva and Jennifer Gonzaga (2020) identify as "A Theory of Human Motivation," provided support for this study's postulated hierarchy of requirements. The needs for love and belonging make up the third level of Maslow's five levels of needs hierarchy. A student needs to feel cared for and loved in order to feel a sense of belonging. They ask their parents for this rather frequently. Parents need to seize every chance to encourage their children to behave well and be interested in what they are studying. A learner's capacity and motivation to learn are substantially increased when these demands are met.

According to Herpratiwi and Ahmad Tohir (2022), learning motivation was most significantly influenced by learning interest. In the process of learning, interest acts as both a strong dictator and motivator. When students' interests and emotions are pleasantly piqued, they are more inclined to participate in educational activities. Learning with a passion is preferable than learning with no passion.

Donbusch et.al (1978) discovered that research has also examined several elements of family dynamics and the relationship between parenting styles and academic motivation. It was shown that less authoritarian and permissive parenting is associated with higher parental education. In a different research by Strage (1999), it was shown that kids were more self-assured, persistent, and positively oriented toward their professors when parents gave them more autonomy, demands, and supports. Pupils that have greater parental autonomy and emotional support generally outperformed their peers and had greater confidence. The most beneficial relationships for grades appear to be those including heavily involved parents and liberal autonomy grant.

Research on the differences between genders in terms of cognitive functions, intellectual skills, interests, stereotypes about daily activities, and task performance has not gotten much attention. There are two hypotheses that explain why men and women

have different personalities. According to the first, men are the ideal human being, and women should be viewed in light of men. The second discourse holds that women represent the less valued affective sphere and males represent the cognitive domain, which is positively regarded in Euro-American culture (Klein, 2004). Biological factors, cultural preconceptions, and/or stereotypes are typically blamed for the academic achievement gaps between boys and girls (Klein, 2004). MeenuDev, Ph.D. (2016) cited this.

When analyzing variations in student accomplishment, gender has been one of the variables that has been reported the most (OECD, 2004; World Bank, 2004; Nguyen and Fahey, 2001; Nguyen, 2002; Rosier, 1978; Williams, Long, Carpenter, and Hayden, 1993). Nevertheless, prior studies on gender variations in student achievement have not consistently produced meaningful findings. The impacts of gender on student accomplishment have been found to differ depending on the country, time period, subject (math or languages), and school level (primary or secondary). Results on the correlation between gender and student achievement among SACMEQ I participating nations have differed. In Malawi, males outperformed girls in reading, as per Milner, Chimombo, Banda, and Mchikoma (2001); Kulpoo (1998) reports that girls in Mauritius did better in reading than boys. However, a 1994 UNESCO research found that gender did not differ in Zimbabwe's reading comprehension (Murimba et al., 1994). According to Keitheile and Mokubung (2005), girls in Botswana outperformed boys in reading and math, with a significant difference between the sexes' reading scores.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of factors affecting the interest in learning among Intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, Ministry of Basic Higher and Technical Education in Sulu during the School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it seeks to find answers to the following queries upon its very completion:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of intermediate Pupil-respondents of Panglima Estino District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education -Sulu as to:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Grade Level;
 - 1.4 Parent's Educational Attainment; and
 - 1.5 Parents Average Monthly Income?
2. What is the extent of the factors affecting the interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education - Sulu in the context of:
 - 2.1 Teacher -Related Factor;
 - 2.2 Pupils- Related Factor; and
 - 2.3 Home – Related Factor?

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the factors affecting the interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education -Sulu when data are grouped according to socio-demographic profile, in terms of:

- 3.1 Age;
- 3.2 Gender;
- 3.3 Grade Level;
- 3.4 Parent's Educational Attainment; and
- 3.5 Parents average monthly income?

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors affecting the interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education –Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Owing that there are hypotheses posited in this study, the descriptive-exploratory research design was used to collect the empirical data.

For the data collection, this study used descriptive survey method to gather information about the factors that affects the interest in learning of intermediate pupils at Panglima Estino District, MBHTE-SULU.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Panglima Estino District, MBHTE-Sulu among intermediate pupils, currently enrolled at Punay E/S, Pandacan E/S, Badjang E/S, Tiptipon E/S School Year for 2023-2024.

A total of one hundred pupil-respondents were taken as respondents for this particular study. It is located in the Municipality of Panglima Estino, Province of Sulu.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the intermediate pupils who are currently enrolled at Punay E/S, Pandacan E/S, Badjang E/S, Tiptipon E/S of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE-Sulu for School Year 2023-2024.

A total of one hundred pupils-respondents were taken as respondents for this particular study.

	Grade 4	Grade 5	Grade 6
PUNAY E/S	8	8	9
PANDACAN E/S	8	8	9
BADJANG E/S	8	8	9
TIPTIPON E/S	8	8	9
Sub total	32	32	36
Overall total: 100			

Sampling Design

The sampling design used in this particular study is the purposive sampling, which means that the researcher chooses the actual respondents of the study to ensure the proper representation of the respondents among the intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE-Sulu for School Year 2023-2024.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the course of gathering the empirical data, a letter duly approved by the Dean of Graduate Studies was sought. The researcher requests a written permission from the school Division Superintendent and Principal before the questionnaire was administered to the intermediate pupils. The researcher personally delivered the questionnaire to the respondents after receiving consent for the request. The pupil- respondents were assured of their privacy. The filled out questionnaire was retrieved on the target date. Permission and assistance from the different teacher-in-charge/class adviser of the different schools of the intermediate pupils was also pursued.

Data and responses obtained and gathered was coded accordingly and was subjected to the expertise of the statistician for appropriate treatment and analysis. Subsequently, the final draft was prepared.

Research Instrument

The study used the descriptive-survey method. The researcher primarily utilized a standardize questionnaire adopted from the study of Farhan Alshammari, Reynita Saguban, Eddieson Pasay-an, Ahmed Altheban, Layla Al-Shammari (2017), as the main data gathering tool. The instrument was adapted for the research with minor modification.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In the course of contextualizing the empirical data, the researcher used weighted mean, frequency count, t-test, while employing the use of statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS). The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized to test the hypothesis.

- 1) For research question 1, the researcher utilized frequency and percentage to determine the profile of the respondents;
- 2) For research question 2, the researcher administered weighted mean and standard deviation for the extent of the factors affecting the interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino, District, Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education-Sulu in the context of; Teacher- Related Factor, Pupils-Related Factor and Home– Related Factor.
- 3) For research Question 3, When data are grouped according to gender, the t-test for independent samples was used to find the significant differences in the extent of the factors affecting the interest in learning; when data are grouped according to age, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income, One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is used;
- 4) For research question 4, To ascertain the significant link between the sub-categories that were subsumed, Pearson Product - Moment link Coefficient (Pearson r) was utilized.

The rating scale intervals listed below were used in the computation results that both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques produced:

Point	Scale Value	Descriptors
5	4.50- 5.00	Always Affect
4	3.50- 4.49	Often Affect
3	2.50-3.49	Sometimes Affect
2	1.50-2.49	Rarely Affect
1	1.00-1.49	Never Affect

RESULTS

1. *What is the socio - demographic profile of the intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE- Sulu in terms of 1.1 age, 1.2 gender, 1.3 grade level, 1.4 parent's educational attainment, and 1.5 parent's average monthly income?*

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. Forty-five percent (45%) of the respondents each are between 10 – 11 years old and 12 – 13 years old. Only four percent (4%) are 14 years old and above.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
9 years old and below	6	6%
10 – 11 years old	45	45%
12 – 13 years old	45	45%
14 years old and above	4	4%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. It showed that equal number were taken as respondents of the study from both male and female pupils.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	50	50%
Female	50	50%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of grade level. It showed that 36% of the respondents belong to Grade 6 while 32 % each were taken from Grade 4 and Grade 5.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 4	32	32%
Grade 5	32	32%
Grade 6	36	36%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of parent's educational attainment. It showed that 48% of the parents reached elementary level in education while 16% reached college level. None of the parents finish masters/ doctorate degree.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	17	17%
Elementary Level	48	48%
Secondary Level	19	19%
College Level	16	16%
Masters/Doctorate Degree	0	0%
TOTAL	100	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Average Monthly Income

Table 1.5 presents the demographic profile of the respondents' in terms of parent's average monthly income. It showed that 51% of the parents earn P5, 000.00 and below each month and only 9% earn P15, 001.00 and above each month.

Table 1.5 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parent's Average Monthly Income

Parent's Average Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
P5,000.00 and below	51	51%
P5,001.00 – 10,000.00	22	22%
P10,001.00 – 15,000.00	18	18%
P15,001.00 and above	9	9%
TOTAL	100	100%

2. What is the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of 2.1 teacher – related factor, 2.2 pupils – related factor, and 2.3 home – related factor?

Table 2.1 presents the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District in the context of teacher – related factor, it showed that the respondents indicated ***always affect*** in all statements in the context of teacher – related factor. These include the following: my teachers use a variety of strategies, teaching aids/devices, and techniques to present the lesson (mean = 5.000, SD =.000); they are structured in their subject matter presentation by methodically adhering to the course routine; and they get along well with both the students and their co-teacher (mean = 5.000, SD =.000). The average mean of 4.963 shows that variables always affect intermediate students' motivation to learn in the Panglima Estino District when teacher-related factors are taken into account.

Table 2.1 Extent of the Factors Affecting Interest in Learning among Intermediate Pupils of Panglima Estino District in the Context of Teacher – Related Factor

Teacher – Related Factor	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My teachers have a good relationship with the pupils and co-teacher.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
2. My teacher enforce the regulations as stated and do not give in to peer pressure.	4.880	.327	Always Affect
3. My teachers are open to suggestion and opinion and is worthy of praise.	4.960	.197	Always Affect
4. My teachers show smartness, confidence, and firmness in making decision.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
5. My teachers have an appealing personality with good sense of humor.	4.960	.197	Always Affect
6. My teachers explain the objectives of the lesson clearly at the start of each period.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
7. My teachers have mastery of subject matter.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
8. My teachers are organized in presenting subject matter by systematically following course routine.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
9. My teachers are updated with present trends relevant to the subject matter.	4.830	.378	Always Affect
10. My teachers show various strategies, teaching aids/devices, and techniques in presenting the lesson.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
AVERAGE	4.963		Always Affect

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always Affect
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often Affect
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes Affect
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely Affect
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never Affect

Table 2.2 presents the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District in the context of pupils – related factor. The respondents indicated **always affect** in almost all statements and among those are; I listen to my teacher well (mean = 5.000, SD = .000); I exert more effort when I do difficult assignment (mean = 5.000, SD = .000); and I want to get good grades on tests, quizzes, assignments, and projects (mean = 4.880, SD = .327). However, they also indicated **often affect** in statement 10 and that is on; I have a specific place to study at home which I keep clean and orderly (mean = 4.300, SD = 1.133). The average mean of 4.615 means that pupils

– related factor *always affect* the intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District in terms of pupils – related factor.

Table 2.2 Extent of the Factors Affecting Interest in Learning among Intermediate Pupils of Panglima Estino District in the Context of Pupils – Related Factor

Pupils – Related Factor	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I listen to my teacher well.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
2. I actively participate in the discussion, answering exercises, and clarifying things I did not understand.	4.710	.456	Always Affect
3. I want to get good grades on tests, quizzes, assignments, and projects.	4.880	.327	Always Affect
4. I make myself prepared for the subject.	4.830	.378	Always Affect
5. I get frustrated when the discussion is interrupted or the teacher is absent.	4.610	.490	Always Affect
6. I exert more effort when I do difficult assignment.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
7. I study the lesson I missed if I were absent from the class.	4.710	.456	Always Affect
8. I study and prepare for quiz and test.	4.830	.378	Always Affect
9. I see to it that extracurricular activities do not hamper my studies.	3.280	1.577	Sometimes Affect
10. I have a specific place to study at home which I keep clean and orderly.	4.300	1.133	Often Affect
AVERAGE	4.615		Always Affect

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always Affect
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often Affect
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes Affect

2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely Affect
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never Affect

Table 2.3 presents the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District in the context of home – related factor.

The respondents indicated **always affect** in almost all statements. Some of those statements are; my parents give me guidance (mean = 5.000, SD = .000); my cellphone helps me in my online school – related searches at home (mean = 4.860, SD = .349); and my parents instill in me the value of good education (mean = 4.880, SD = .327). However, the respondents indicated **rarely affect** in statement 3 and that is on; my parents hire a private tutor for me (mean = 2.080, SD = 1.339). The average mean of 4.434 means that the home – related factor **often affect** the interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District in the context of home – related factor.

Table 2.3 Extent of the Factors Affecting Interest in Learning among Intermediate Pupils of Panglima Estino District in the Context of Home – Related Factor

Home – Related Factor	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. My parents motivated me to improve my studies.	4.830	.378	Always Affect
2. My parents provide learning materials (books, dictionary) suitable for my learning.	4.540	.771	Always Affect
3. My parents hire a private tutor for me.	2.080	1.339	Rarely Affect
4. My parents help me in my homework.	4.660	.755	Always Affect
5. My parents give me guidance.	5.000	.000	Always Affect
6. My siblings do not disturb me when I am studying my lessons.	3.950	1.351	Often Affect
7. My cellphone helps me in my online school – related searches at home.	4.860	.349	Always Affect
8. My parents instill in me the value of good education.	4.880	.327	Always Affect
9. My parents attend our school meeting and activities.	4.830	.378	Always Affect
10. My parents experience financial problem.	4.710	.456	Always Affect
AVERAGE	4.434		Often Affect

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always Affect
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often Affect
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes Affect

2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely Affect
1	1.00 – 1.49	Never Affect

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to age, gender, grade level, parent’s educational attainment, and parents average monthly income?

3.1 By Gender

Table 3.1 shows the differences in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender.

The t-test was used for gender since there are only two categories. The sig. value of 0.469 for teacher – related factor is greater than the p – value of .05, the sig. value of .790 for pupil – related factor was greater than the p – value at .05, and the sig. value of 0.615 for home – related factor is also greater than the p = .05, 2- tailed tests. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There is no significant difference in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE- Sulu when data are grouped according to their gender.

Table 3.1 t – test for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Factors Affecting Interest in Learning among Intermediate Pupils of Panglima Estino District in terms of Gender

Variables	Grouping	Mean		Diff.	t	Sig.	Description
		Mean	SD				
Teacher – related factor	Male	4.150	.630	.220	28.490	.469	Not
	Female	3.930	.750				Significant
Pupil – related factor	Male	3.950	.550	.170	29.150	.790	Not
	Female	3.780	.720				Significant
Home – related factor	Male	4.210	.810	.230	28.650	.615	Not
	Female	3.980	.790				Significant

Table 3.2 presents the ANOVA for significant difference in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District in terms of age, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income.

The sig. value of 0.668 for age, the sig. value of 0.367 for grade level, the sig. value of 0.282 for parent's educational attainment, and the sig. value of 0.281 for parent's average monthly income were all greater than the p – value of .05. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

There are no significant differences in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District when data are group according to their grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income.

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Factors Affecting Interest in Learning Among Intermediate Pupils of Panglima Estino District in terms of Age, Grade Level, Parent's educational Attainment, and Parent's Average Monthly Income

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.	Description
Age						
Between Groups	.117	3	0.039	0.267	.668	Not Significant
Within Groups	13.993	96	0.146			
TOTAL	14.110	99				
Grade Level						
Between Groups	.216	2	0.108	1.009	.367	Not Significant
Within Groups	10.344	97	0.107			
TOTAL	10.560	99				
Parent's Educational Attainment						
Between Groups	6.334	4	1.584	0.628	.282	Not Significant
Within Groups	239.826	95	2.524			
TOTAL	246.160	99				
Parent's Average Monthly Income						
Between Groups	.388	3	0.129	1.316	.281	Not Significant
Within Groups	9.378	96	0.098			
TOTAL	9.765	99				

Significant at .05

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of teacher – related factor, pupils – related factor, and home – related factor?

Pearson Product – Moment Correlation or Pearson r was used to determine if there is a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of teacher – related factor, pupils – related factor, and home – related factor.

The average value of $r = 0.449$ for teacher – related factor was interpreted as **moderate correlation** while the average value of $r = 0.313$ for pupils – related factor was interpreted as **moderate correlation** at significant value of .05 two- tailed test, and the average value of .389 for home – related factor was also interpreted as **moderate correlation**.

Table 4. Significant Correlation in the Extent of the Factors Affecting Interest in Learning Among Intermediate Pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu in the Context of Teacher – Related Factor, Pupils – Related Factor, and Home – Related Factor

		Pearson r	Sig.	n	Description
Teacher – Related Factor	Pupils – related factor	.578	.000	100	High
	Home – related factor	.319	.000	100	Moderate
	AVERAGE	.449			MODERATE
Pupils – Related Factor	Teacher – related factor	.462	.000	100	Moderate
	Home – related factor	.163	.000	100	Low
	AVERAGE	.313			MODERATE

Home – Related Factor	Teacher – related factor	.496	.000	100	Moderate
	Pupils – related factor	.281	.000	100	Low
	AVERAGE	.389			MODERATE

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at $\alpha = .05$

Correlation Scales adapted from Hopkins (2002):

0.0 – 0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1 – 0.3 = Low; 0.3 – 0.5 = Moderate; 0.5 – 0.7 = High;
0.7 – 0.9 = Very High; 0.9 – 1.0 = Nearly Perfect

DISCUSSION

1. On the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income

The result showed that almost half of the respondents are either between 10 - 11 years old or between 12 – 13 years old. Equal number of respondents were taken from each gender. Grade 6 pupils were slightly higher than Grades 4 and 5 as respondents of the study. Almost half of the parents were able to attend elementary level only in education and more than half earns P5,000.00 and below each month.

It implies that the intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District are in the right age for their present grade level. The parents are not very educated and belong to low income families.

2. On the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District MBHTE – Sulu in the context of teacher – related factor, pupils – related factor, and home – related factor

The intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District are **always affected** by the teacher – related factor and pupils – related factor. Home – related factor showed that they are **often affected** by it.

The result implies that the different factors greatly affect the interest in learning among the intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District.

Ratnasari (2017) emphasized that interest in learning greatly influences student achievement. According to Suprihatin (2015), the teacher is an important or influential figure because they must foster learning motivation in students for optimal and maximum learning outcomes in any way including creativity as a teacher.

3. *On the Significant difference in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to age, gender, grade level, parent’s educational attainment, and parents average monthly income*

There is no significant difference in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, grade level, parent’s educational attainment, and parent’s average monthly income. However, a significant difference in terms of age existed.

The result implies that the different demographic profiles of the intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District cannot predict the extent of the factors that affect their interest in learning except in terms of age.

According to a World Bank study done in Vietnam in 2004, students who were older than their classmates typically performed worse in math and language. However, a study by Sirin (2005), referenced by Ngussa and Gundula (2019), found that children of high socioeconomic status parents appear to do better than pupils whose parents are from lower socioeconomic classes. Academic achievement has been found to be influenced by parents' educational attainment.

4. *On the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District, MBHTE – Sulu in the context of teacher – related factor, pupils – related factor, and home – related factor*

There is a ***moderate correlation*** among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District in the context of teacher – related factor, pupils – related factor, and home – related factor.

The result simply implies that the different factors affect the interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District to some extent.

Simbolon (2014) as cited by Sobandi (2016) stressed that a teacher plays an important role in arousing students’ interest in learning so that they are involved in lessons with enthusiasm and encourage them to participate directly in learning.

Students' lack of desire to study affects their academic performance because of low self-esteem, unmet expectations in the classroom, feeling abandoned or unsupported by the family, and extreme pressure (Greate School, 2015). Egalite (2016) asserts that there is a high association between a student's familial history and academic achievement, and that differences in the school or community may be the primary factor influencing these relationships.

Conclusions

The intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District attended school as prescribed by MBHTE-BARMM, with most parents who did not finish even high school, and earns below the minimum every month.

It only showed that teacher – related factor, pupils – related factor, and home – related factor does affect the interest in learning among intermediate pupils at Panglima Estino District. Hence, the academic achievement of the learners is also affected.

The absence of difference in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District when data are grouped according to gender, grade level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's average monthly income only proves that profiles of the intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District is not a determinant that affects interest in learning.

The moderate correlation in the extent of the factors affecting interest in learning among intermediate pupils of Panglima Estino District could only mean that the different factors are interrelated to one another to some extent.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. Further study on the extent of the effect of the different factors in the interest in learning among pupils must be conducted to really prove their effect on pupil's academic achievement.
2. Future researchers on the same topic should add variables like study habits and other variables not covered by this study.
3. Teachers should constantly encourage learners to do their best in school and study harder to achieve better grades.
4. Teachers should give their best in teaching the learners and should serve as an inspiration and role model for learners to look up to.
5. Parents should provide a home that is conducive to learning and must always get involved in their children's education.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

First and foremost, each participant received a thorough informed consent form outlining the study's objectives, procedures, possible benefits and hazards, and confidentiality guidelines. Moreover, in instances where the trial outcomes were unaffected by the respondents' personal details, every trial data point was meticulously anonymized. To protect participant privacy, data collection was done in a private setting,

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